

for 0.5 h a deep red coloured azo dye was separated out. It was crystallised from ethanol (50%), m.p. 172° (Found : S, 13 ; N, 19.87. C₂₂H₁₇N₇S₂O₃ requires S, 13.03 ; N, 19.95%). The physical and analytical data of benzylidene-thiazolidinones, their dibromides and sulphonamido derivatives have been shown in Table 1.

Hydrolysis of thiazolidinone 2f: A mixture of the thiazolidinone (0.5 g) in rectified spirit (25 ml) and concentrated HCl (6 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 8 h. Excess of alcohol was distilled off and the residue extracted with boiling water. The water insoluble component corresponding to 3-cyclopentyl-2,4-thiazolidione gave m.p. 166-67° (Found : S, 17.03. C₈H₁₁NSO₂ requires S, 17.29%).

The aqueous solution was basified by dilute NaOH solution and extracted with ether. The evaporation of ether left an oily mass corresponding to aniline.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF BENZYLIDENE DIBROMIDE AND SULPHONAMIDO DERIVATIVES

Compd.	Benzylidene (3)		Dibromide (4)		Sulphonamido (5)	
	M.p. °C	S % : Found/ (Calcd.)	M.p. °C	Br % : Found/ (Calcd.)	M.p. °C	S % : Found/ (Calcd.)
d	>250	800 (8.08)	206	29.00 (29.09)	172	13.00 (13.03)
e	230	7.50 (8.30)	—	—	—	—
f	124	8.50 (9.10)	239	37.42 (37.38)	195	21.50 (21.71)
g	165	8.52 (8.83)	240	36.01 (36.18)	212	21.10 (21.05)
h	184	8.23 (8.51)	>250	35.16 (35.09)	240	20.28 (20.42)
i	224	6.52 (6.77)	152	24.32 (24.53)	—	—
j	118	6.82 (7.00)	253	—	—	—
k	187	6.10 (6.27)	>250	—	—	—

Hydrolysis of 2g and 2h gave 3-cyclohexyl-2,4-thiazolidione (m.p. 164°) and 3-cycloheptyl-2,4-thiazolidione (m.p. 159°), respectively along with aniline. On the other hand the hydrolysis of 2i, 2j and 2k furnished imidazopyrimidoamine, 9-aminoacridine and diphenylaminopyrimidine, respectively. 3-Phenyl-2,4-thiazolidione, m.p. 201° (lit.⁴ 200-201°) was also obtained along with the amines.

3-Cyclohexylimino-5-dimethylaminomethyl-4-thiazolidinone (6b): A mixture of 2b (0.5 g) and dimethylamine (1 ml) in dilute HCl (5 ml) was refluxed gently during which formalin (1 ml) was added dropwise. After a period of 2 h it was cooled and the separated precipitate was basified with ammonia and kept overnight. The solid obtained was washed with water and dried (40%), m.p. 125° (Found : S, 10.21. C₁₇H₂₂N₃SO requires S, 10.09%). 6f (m.p. 144°) and 6g (m.p. 154°) were prepared from 3f and 2g, respectively.

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Synthesis of 5-Methoxy-1,3-disubstituted-benzimidazolin-2-thiones as Potential Biologically Active Agents†

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BENZIMIDAZOLES have been reported to possess wide range of biological activity, such as antibacterial¹, antifungal², anthelmintic^{3,4}, antiviral activity^{5,6}. 5-Methoxybenzimidazolin-2-thione (I) as well as cyclised products from I also exhibited antibacterial activity⁷. In consideration of these observations the synthesis of the title compounds and their evaluation as antiviral agents against *Sunnehmp rosette* virus has been undertaken.

The synthesis of 5-methoxybenzimidazolin-2-thione (I)⁸ was achieved by the reaction of 4-methoxy-*o*-phenylenediamine^{10,11} and CS₂ in presence of ethanolic KOH. The title compounds were synthesised from I by reacting it with 40% aqueous formaldehyde solution and various amines under the condition of Mannich reaction. I was also acylated to get 1,3-diacetyl-5-methoxy-benzimidazolin-2-thione (3).

The ir spectrum of 2a showed characteristic bands at 2820 (CH₂), 1220 (C=S) and 1110 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C). Its nmr spectrum was in accord with assigned structures. Peaks (δ) were observed at 2.6-2.7 (8H, -CH₂-O-CH₂), 3.5-3.6 (8H-N<CH₂),

†Part XLV of the series "Potential Biologically Active Agents".

3.7 (3H₁-CH₃), 4.9 (4H, N-CH₂-N) and 6.7-7.3 (3H, ArH).

The mass spectrum of compound 2a exhibited an intense molecular ion peak 1 at *m/e* 378. The molecular ion peak then undergoes McLafferty

1,3-Bis(aceto)-5-methoxybenzimidazolin-2-thione (3): 1 (2.0 g) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (5 ml) for 1 h. The content were poured in water (100 ml). Crystallisation of the product from methanol yielded pure 3 (50%), m.p. 150°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1700 (C=O), 1220 (C=S) and 1105 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C).

TABLE 1—5-METHOXY-1,3-DISUBSTITUTED BENZIMIDAZOLIN-2-THIONES

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Molecular formula*	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			% inhibition of SRV**	
			C	H	N	<i>in vitro</i>	<i>in vivo</i>
2a	105	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₃ S	56.65 (57.14)	6.44 (6.87)	—	35	23
2b	107	C ₂₀ H ₃₀ N ₄ OS.1/2H ₂ O	62.40 (62.66)	8.39 (8.09)	—	41	37
2c	135	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₄ OS	67.80 (67.69)	5.60 (5.64)	—	51	34
2d	133	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₄ OCl ₂ S.1/2H ₂ O	56.80 (56.41)	4.72 (4.48)	—	15	Nil
2e	140	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ OBr ₂ S	48.35 (48.17)	3.69 (3.64)	—	38	23
2f	102	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ N ₄ OS.1/2H ₂ O	67.45 (67.44)	5.92 (6.32)	—	53	41
2g	125	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₃ S	63.80 (64.00)	5.40 (5.77)	—	49	32
2h	230	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₅ S	54.80 (55.00)	4.54 (4.16)	—	46	35
2i	220	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₅ S	—	—	12.03 (11.92)	Nil	Nil
2j	205	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₅ S	61.10 (61.66)	5.18 (5.12)	—	Nil	Nil
2k	180	C ₂₈ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₅ S	62.95 (62.92)	5.18 (5.61)	—	13	8
2l	115	C ₃₀ H ₃₆ N ₆ O ₅ S	64.40 (64.28)	6.32 (6.42)	—	46	41
2m	105	C ₃₂ H ₄₀ N ₆ OS.H ₂ O	67.35 (66.89)	7.45 (7.31)	—	23	11
2n	175	C ₃₂ H ₃₈ N ₆ O ₅ S	—	—	13.50 (13.63)	46	38
2o	192	C ₃₄ H ₄₀ N ₆ O ₅ S	—	—	13.62 (13.72)	62	43
3	150	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₅ S	54.40 (54.54)	4.71 (4.54)	—	44	38

* All compounds recrystallised from CHCl₃ and petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), yield 50-60%.

** Tricothecium polysaccharide (standard potent compound) exhibited 90% inhibition of TMV under the same condition in both *in vitro* and *in vivo*.

rearrangement yielding peak 2 at *m/e* 279 and a neutral fragment (m.w. 99).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 137 and 177 spectrophotometers in KBr, and nmr on a Varian A-60D instrument in CDCl₃ using TMS as internal reference. Mass spectrum was recorded on a Hitachi RMU-6 spectrometer at 70 eV.

1,3-Bis(morpholino)methyl-5-methoxybenzimidazolin-2-thiones (2a): 1 (0.90 g, 0.005 mol) was taken in methanol (10 ml) formalin (0.5 ml) and morpholine (0.5 ml) were added to it with warming and shaking. The product which separated on scratching the sides of flask was filtered and crystallised from chloroform and petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) (0.90 g, 50%), m.p. 105°, *m/e* 378 (M⁺), 279, 193, 180, 165, 149, 148, 100.

Antiviral activity against Sunnhemp rosette virus (SRV) (a strain of TMV) :

The culture of Sunnhemp rosette virus (SRV) was maintained by successive host inoculation (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba*) plants. The procedure of Mukerjee *et al.*⁹ was followed for *in vitro* and *in vivo* antiviral testing.

All the synthesised compounds were dissolved in their respective solvent. These solutions were termed "test solutions". The percentage of inhibition was expressed as,

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = \frac{C-T}{C} \times 100$$

where, C=number of lesions on control leaves and T=number of lesions on treated leaves.

It is evident that majority of the synthesised compounds inhibited growth of SRV *in vitro* and *in vivo* (Table 1). The compounds 2c, 2f, 2g, 3, 2n and 2o exhibited significant activity.

Chemical Studies on *Ailanthus excelsa*

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- 2
 a, A = morpholino
 b, A = piperidino
 c, A = anilino
 d, A = 4-Cl-anilino
 e, A = 4-Br-anilino
 f, A = 4-CH₃-anilino
 g, A = 4-OCH₃-anilino
 h, A = 4-NO₂-anilino
 i, A = 4-COOH-anilino
 j, A = 4-COOH₂-anilino
 k, A = 4-COOC₂H₅-anilino
 l, A = 4-(N-morpholino)anilino
 m, A = 4-(N-piperidino)anilino
 n, A = 4-(N-morpholinocarbonyl)anilino
 o, A = 4-(N-piperidinocarbonyl)anilino

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QUASSINOIDS, a monopoly of the family *Simarubaceae*, have gained extensive importance in view of their potent antileukaemic activity. In a recent communication¹, we reported the presence of a new quassinoid, 1 : 12-deoxy-13-formylailanthinol from the stem bark of *Ailanthus excelsa*, a simarubous plant. We now report the occurrence of excelsin² from its root bark and describe its spectral details, viz. ir, uv, ¹Hnmr, mass, and ¹³Cnmr (the latter not reported for this compound so far).

Sun-dried rootbark of *Ailanthus excelsa* was collected from the outskirts of Patna (Bihar), powdered, defatted with petrol, and then thoroughly extracted with rectified spirit in a soxhlet. The systematic chromatographic fractionation of the alcoholic extract over silicic acid led to the isolation of excelsin (0.0005%), m.p. 268-270°, crystallised as light white needles from methanol, C₂₈H₃₆O₉; λ_{max} (MeOH) 205 nm (lack of conjugation); ν_{max} (nujol) 3300-3450 (OH), 1750, 1720 (lactonyl and ester carbonyls), 1455, 1375 cm⁻¹; δ (pyridine-d₅) (3.60 (1H, d, J8Hz, 1-H), 4.55 (1H, m, 2-H), 5.73 (1H, br s, 3-H), 1.54 (3H, s, 4-CH₃), 4.68 (1H, t,

TABLE 1

Carbon number	Glucarubin (DMSO-d ₆)	Excelsin (DMSO-d ₆)
1	82.6	82.6 (d)
2	71.3	71.3 (d)
3	125.7	125.8 (d)
4	133.8	133.8 (s)
5	40.1	40.1 (d)
6	24.9	24.8 (t)
7	77.9	77.9 (d)
8	46.7	46.8 (s)
9	40.9	41.0 (d)
10	44.1 ^a	44.2 (s)
11	109.1	109.2 (s)
12	78.5	78.4 (d)
13	31.4	31.4 (d)
14	44.6 ^a	44.4 (d)
15	69.5	68.9 (d)
16	167.1	167.4 (s)
17	70.1	70.2 (t)
18	14.8	14.6 (q)
19	10.1	9.7 (q)
20	20.9	20.8 (q)
Side Chain		
1'	170.4	170.3 (s)
2'	73.9	39.5 (d)
3'	32.6	26.2 (t)
4'	7.7	11.1 (q)
5'	24.9	15.8 (q)

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